

**Correction to: Principles of Surgical Treatment
of Soft Tissue Sarcomas (Cancers, (2025),
17, 3, (401), 10.3390/cancers17030401)**

Item Type	info:eu-repo/semantics/article
Authors	Gonzalez, Marcos R.; Mendez-Guerra, Carolina; Goh, Megan H.; Pretell-Mazzini, Juan
DOI	https://doi.org/10.3390/cancers17132096
Publisher	Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI)
Journal	Cancers
Rights	info:eu-repo/semantics/openAccess
Download date	23/04/2026 20:25:45
Item License	http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
Link to Item	http://hdl.handle.net/10757/687668

Correction

Correction: Gonzalez et al. Principles of Surgical Treatment of Soft Tissue Sarcomas. *Cancers* 2025, 17, 401

Marcos R. Gonzalez ¹

¹ Division of Orthopaedic Oncology, Department of Orthopaedic Surgery, Massachusetts General Hospital, Harvard Medical School, Boston, MA 02115, USA

² Facultad de Ciencias de la Salud, Universidad Peruana de Ciencias Aplicadas, Lima 15067, Peru

³ Division of Orthopedic Oncology, Miami Cancer Institute, Baptist Health System South Florida, Plantation, FL 33324, USA

⁴ Department of Orthopaedic Surgery, Herbert Wertheim College of Medicine, Florida International University, Miami, FL 33199, USA

* Correspondence: juan.pretell@baptisthealth.net

In the original publication [1], there was a mistake: Table 3 and its citations in the main text were missing. The correct Table 3 and its caption appear below. The citations for Table 3 have been added in 3.1. *Margin Assessment*.

The authors state that the scientific conclusions are unaffected. This correction was approved by the Academic Editor. The original publication has also been updated.

Received: 14 May 2025
Accepted: 30 May 2025
Published: 23 June 2025

Citation: Gonzalez, M.R.; Mendez-Guerra, C.; Goh, M.H.; Pretell-Mazzini, J. Correction: Gonzalez et al. Principles of Surgical Treatment of Soft Tissue Sarcomas. *Cancers* 2025, 17, 401. *Cancers* 2025, 17, 2096. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cancers17132096>

Copyright: © 2025 by the authors. Licensee MDPI, Basel, Switzerland. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Table 3. Classification systems for surgical margins in STS.

MSTS [69]		AJCC (R Classification) [70]	UICC (R + 1 mm Classification) [71]	TMCC [72]	
Margin Class	Plane of Dissection	Margin Class	Description	Margin Class	Description
Radical	Extracompartmental <i>en bloc</i> entire compartment	R0	Tumor does not reach intact barrier or resection margins	Negative	Tumor does not reach intact barrier or resection margins
Wide	Intracompartmental <i>en bloc</i> with cuff of normal tissue	R1	Microscopic residual tumor	Planned closure	Positive surgical margins against one or more critical structures (nerve, vessel or bone) which had been planned preoperatively as part of a primary resection
Marginal	Shell out <i>en bloc</i> through pseudocapsule or reactive zone	R2	Macroscopic residual tumor	Positive after prior unplanned excision	Positive margin on tumor bed re-excision
Intralesional	Piecemeal debulking or curettage			Unplanned positive margins	Positive margin which had not been planned

AJCC: American Joint Committee on Cancer (R classification); MSTS: Musculoskeletal Tumor Society; UICC: Union for International Cancer Control; TMCC: Toronto Margin Context Classification.

Reference

1. Gonzalez, M.R.; Mendez-Guerra, C.; Goh, M.H.; Pretell-Mazzini, J. Principles of Surgical Treatment of Soft Tissue Sarcomas. *Cancers* **2025**, *17*, 401. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]

Disclaimer/Publisher’s Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of MDPI and/or the editor(s). MDPI and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.